

Automated data screening and data quality checks using the R package dataquieR

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Background / Introduction

A statistician's analysis workflow usually begins with the checking and cleaning of a data body before proceeding to any substantive scientific analyses. This starting point frequently consumes a large part of the analysis resources. This work shows how the efficiency and transparency of this essential step in the analysis workflow can be improved based on the recently updated R dataquieR package.

Methods

The R package dataquieR consists of almost 20 core functions and more than 250 support functions, which enable an automated creation of complex reports. The support functions also ensure robustness to a priori unknown data errors. For the output, dataquieR renders HTML files using htmltools and uses plotly to enable interactive graphs. The package is available on the comprehensive R archive network (CRAN) [1].

Results

dataquieR integrates a wide range of data checks in a one-stop-shop, including, amongst others descriptive statistics, range and contradiction checks, unit and item missingness overviews, univariate and multivariate outlier assessments, checks of expected associations and distributions, mixed models and nonparametric regression techniques to inspect observer, device or centre effects, as well as time trends. Assessments are controlled based on a metadata model containing knowledge and assumptions about (1) individual variables (e.g. range violations, expected range of point estimates), (2) groups of variables (e.g. contradictions), (3) data segments (e.g. expected case count in an examination), (4) data tables (e.g. expected variable selection), (5) classification of missing codes by linking study specific missing value codes with a generic ontology. Each metadata table can be treated as a spreadsheet in an Excel workbook for easy editing. The contained information triggers the entire analysis pipeline or selected parts of it. dataquieR has been applied to cohort study as well as health registry data.

Conclusion

The workflow implemented in dataquieR illustrates an often neglected approach: the systematic separation of assumptions and knowledge underlying analyses from the actual analysis code. Adhering to this separation not only increases efficacy, but also contributes to a more systematic implementation and significantly greater transparency of data quality checks and their reporting.

[1] Kasbohm E, Marino J, Salogni E, Richter A, Schmidt CO, Struckmann S. dataquieR: Data Quality in Epidemiological Research. 2024. Available from: <https://cran.r-project.org/package=dataquieR>